

Subject: Sports**Title:** Evaluating Sports policy of Manipur 1992**Authors:****Tenzing Singh Ngasham**

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LYCEUM INDIA**Journal of Social Sciences****Abstract:**

After 1972 statehood, Manipur participate in national and international games and sports event. For the first time Manipuri players participated National games in 1985; Olympic games in 1984; Asian games in 1986 and commonwealth Games in 2000s. continuously, in significant ways Manipur produced 19 Olympians, numerous Asian Games champions and commonwealth champion and becoming powerhouse of sports in India. The study will analysis the objectives of Sports Policy of Manipur 1992 by using quantitative and qualitative analysis. Finally, observation and recommendation will highlight in the concluding segment.

Keywords:

Sports Policy of Manipur 1992, Manipur, Olympic Games.

Introduction

In Manipur, sports have existed since ancient times. Sagol Kangjei, Thang Ta & Sarit Sarak, Khong Kangjei, Yubi Lakpi, Mukna, Hiyang Tannaba, and Kang are among the most well-liked traditional games. The state's traditional sport, Sagol Kangjei, is credited with giving rise to the contemporary game of polo (Manipur Tourism, n.d.) Remarkably in the modern context Manipur has produced 19 Olympian including two medallist Mirabai Chanu, silver medal in Tokyo 2020 in weightlifting and Mary Kom, bronze medal in London Olympic 2012 in boxing (Hanjabam & Singh, 2022).

Objectives

1. To examine the comprehensive overview of the Sports Policy of Manipur 1992.
2. To analyses the main focus area of the Sports Policy of Manipur 1992 like infrastructure, promoting indigenous games, talent identification, institutional supports, etc.

Research Questions

1. What is the comprehensive overview of the Sports Policy of Manipur 1992?
2. What is the main focus area of the Sports Policy of Manipur 1992 like infrastructure, promoting indigenous games, talent identification, institutional supports, etc.?

Methodology

Quantitative and qualitative approach of study are used to explore the Sports Policy of Manipur 1992. Furthermore, for a deep analysis the work depends on both primary and secondary sources of data from Department of Youth Affairs and Sports Government of Manipur and other related raw data, news article, scholarly article, etc.

Policy analysis

There is a lot of potential for the advancement of sports and games. The state of Manipur can generate outstanding athletes of international quality if sufficient infrastructure facilities are built and suitable incentives are provided to gifted athletes. Therefore, a STATE SPORTS POLICY has been written in compliance with the Indian government's 1984 National Sports Policy. The local situation and the state's interests have also been considered in the policy (Government of Manipur, Department of Youth Affairs & Sports, n.d.). The State shall try to achieve the following points below:

1. Without the creation of the best sporting facilities, such as playgrounds, indoor halls, swimming pools, gymnasiums, and velodromes, no program promoting sports and physical education can be successful. In order to eventually serve the entire state, these facilities will be supplied in phases. The State Sports Association will be urged to create a time-bound action plan that will include the creation of playfields and

- open spaces for sports as well as their preservation in rural and urban areas.
2. It is a well-established truth that athletes' performance can be improved by eating a healthy diet. Therefore, efforts must be made to guarantee that the food offered has the nutritional value required to satisfy the individual's and various games' unique requirements. athletes.
 3. Talent among young men and women from urban, rural, and tribal communities will be sought for. The selected athletes will receive appropriate nurturing and training to achieve excellence. For this purpose, only, one cell will be opened in each district. The state must create institutions capable of identifying, nurturing, and developing gifted athletes to the fullest extent possible.
 4. Physical education and sports will be integrated into the curriculum as required subjects for school and college exams.
 5. Those who achieve in athletics will receive sufficient rewards. Employment, self-employment, and entrance to educational institutions will all be given special consideration. Incentives for coaches will also be taken into account, taking into account their contributions to helping athletes reach their full potential. Adventure sports and indigenous games will be given special consideration for prizes.
 6. When it comes to competitive sports, the State Sports Associations are particularly accountable. To uphold the dignity of the State and the Nation, they will be urged to project a cohesive and unified image. Therefore, by guaranteeing appropriate and timely selection, such associations will be encouraged to organize frequent State Level tournaments and carry out efficient strategies for preparing State teams for participation in National Level competitions. Additionally, after evaluating the state teams' success in the State Games and via coaching and training, they must make sure that they are funded for National Level tournaments. The State will organize regular games for athletes with disabilities, the elderly, and seasoned athletes.
 7. To developed in the Olympic-recognized disciplines, Asian and Commonwealth Games, Games that are recognized globally and for which there are World Federations, Games for which there are no World Federations.
 8. To protect and promote Manipur's indigenous martial arts and games as an integral part of our culture and to ask for particular attention on a global scale.
 9. Sports in which Manipur may perform exceptionally well at the state, national, and international levels will receive particular emphasis.
 10. To enhance the performance level and for effective training and coaching on scientific lines, a long-term Action Plan shall be drawn up. Coaching Centres at suitable place shall be opened with modern facilities. If necessary, expert from developed countries shall be engaged for the priority games.
 11. After a thorough evaluation of each athlete and, if applicable, the team, the state teams will be funded to compete at the National/Zonel level in an effort to boost performance levels.
 12. Since the government cannot develop and promote sports and physical education on its own, non-governmental organizations, institutions, and individuals should be encouraged to make voluntary efforts to promote sports, both in terms of competitive sports and widespread participation in sports activities.
 13. to evaluate and quantify our top athletes' biological fitness and potential. There will be a single research cell that is furnished with every piece of contemporary sports science equipment.
 14. Offering rewards to athletes is crucial to promoting sports and gaming activities. In this context, the government department's employment opportunities are thought to be the most crucial. All state government departments may set aside a portion of vacation time for the appointment of qualified athletes and will prioritize hiring athletes for appropriate positions.
 15. It shall be the endeavour of the state Government to see that there is only one association for each discipline of sports to avoid problems that may arise out of the existence of more than one association.
 16. A program for the well-being of athletes in distress will be implemented. The program benefits athletes, both active and retired, who have excelled in sports and received awards at various levels.
 17. In keeping with the motto "Catch them young," the state government will make an effort to designate or establish an independent body to identify young people with athletic aptitude.
 18. The government will find sponsors to pay for some athletes to compete at the national and international levels.
 19. It is impossible to efficiently organize many sports and events without an adequate supply of advanced equipment. In order to fulfil these demands, the State Government will thus place a high focus on acquiring sufficient, cutting-edge, scientific equipment.
 20. In order to serve the interests of all district sports enthusiasts, the state government will work to establish an Apex Sports Association at the district level. This District Apex body will be associated with the State Apex body.

21. The Sports Department may need to increase funding and expand its current workforce in order to properly perform its duties.
22. Sports awareness in the state will be maintained and expanded through the use of the mass media.
23. After the amount of time deemed necessary, the State Government may reconsider any provision and/or the policy in its whole.

Conclusion

Sports Policy of Manipur 1992 was the first landmark foundation for the development of games and sports in Manipur. The policy focus on talent identification in both hill and valley and promoting disciplines recognised by Olympic Games, Asian and Commonwealth Games, Games that are recognised globally and for which there are World Federations, Games for which there are no World Federations. Furthermore, the policy focus for promoting indigenous games like *sagol kangjei* (Modern game Polo). The groundwork like infrastructure development especially the khuman lampak sports complex was introduced.

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